

SOM 1

Equipment and settings:

<i>Imaging technique</i>	<i>Equipment</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Resolution</i>	<i>Acquisition method</i>	<i>Software version</i>
Photography	Nikon DSLR D160	Nikon AF-S VR Micro-Nikkor 105 mm f/2.8G IF-ED			
3D scanning	3D structured-light scanner, Aicon SmartScan-HE R8 (now part of Hexagon AB)		Field of View: 110 × 80 × 70mm , 33 μm point-to-point distance	structured-light, ~16 scans on automatic turn table	OptoCat 2018R1
3D digital microscopy	ZEISS Smartzoom 5	PlanApo D 1.6×/NA 0.1,WD 36 mm	Field of View: 10.475 × 7.856 mm (34x)	White LED, reflected ringlight, EDF / Stitching	Smartzoom software with Shuttle&Find module
CT-scannig*	Phoenix V tome x L				

*Move detail about setting on *link*